

PHYSICAL EXERCISE IS THE WORK OF THE DEVIL (PALAISTRICA DIABOLI NEGOTIUM)

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Abstract:

In this study, a decision taken by the Ministry of Education of the implementation of school-aged children's cognitive, physical and sensory effects on the development of physical education is aimed to discuss the future of the teaching profession. In 2014, the Ministry of Education took a decision in favor of the gradual abolition of Technical High School, Technical High School, Vocational School, Vocational High School, and Anatolian Vocational High School of Health Physical Education classes. "*Physical exercise is the devil's work*" said the Catholic church in the medieval process of physical education and sport for hundreds of years had put bans. With the Enlightenment, these prohibitions began to unravel. In Europe In the beginning of secularization efforts in Europe, it showed itself in sports, science, culture and art. Today, our country in which we have been experiencing it is enough to check it out the relevant articles of the Constitution. It is very clear that abolition of physical education classes in vocational high schools is contrary to the Basic Law of National Education and Constitution. As a result, Abolishing of physical education in vocational courses obesity, inactiveness, and behavior in school-aged youth is a widespread concern. It is very clear that physical education classes in the training program which has been the first underestimated lesson from the first lesson. It reveals the malign perspective of Ministry of Education. By reducing of lesson hours and then abolishing of the courses, physical education teachers will be become stranger to applying the job, expanding of sport activities.

Keywords: physical education, teacher, lesson

1. Introduction

In the first years of the Republic, there were no sports areas, no gymnasiums for schools for physical education classes. There were not too many sports equipment. There were gymnastics, games with ball, physical exercises and some military exercises appropriate

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to the widespread understanding of the period (Jahn Gymnastics) in places covered with dust and dirt. In the vast majority of schools, the appropriate areas, halls and sporting equipment for sports training are insufficient. Concrete ground of schools is saved from dust and dirt, but not suitable for children, and causes injuries. Top it all off, in every academic year, teachers make free with students due to they want money from them as "sports fee" in order to buy balls. 100 years later, the members of the Board of Education and Discipline have decided that these courses are preventing the education of "faithful youth" and they abrogated it. Maybe they had a good start. It is better to do nothing at all than to do it like this. *"The task of education in this context is to ensure that people use their minds consistently; make reach them to the gospels; to provide adaptation to universal truth; make them free and happy"* Sönmez (2008). In this example, it seen that this situation does not work for us.

Ministry of National Education Board of Education and Discipline gradually abrogated Physical Education Course in 2013-2014 Academic Year from Technical High School, Anatolian Technical High School, Vocational High School, Anatolian Vocational High School and Anatolian Medical Vocational High School with the decision of Directorate General For Vocational and Technical Education numbered 59917357/101.03/390264.

Throughout the ages, one of the people's greatest hobbies is sports. When industry, economy and politics took the sport as prisoner, powers in institutions such as the Board of Education and Discipline sometimes want to ingratiate themselves so that we are surprised to read. The power holders are also have fun with the situation. It is necessary to examine this execution which will leave hundreds of thousands of students deprived of physical education course, will revoke the right to do sports and leave thousands of teachers with the excess norm.

Catholic Church which said *"Physical Exercise Is the Work of the Devil (Palaistrica Diaboli Negotium)"* Fişek (1985) imposes bans to hundreds of physical education and sport in the middle ages. These bans began to be resolved together with the age of Enlightenment. Secularization efforts started in sport, science, culture and art in Europe manifested itself.

It was not easy to break understanding and executions of Middle Age Europe that considered soul and body were in constant conflict, when they giving priority to spiritual supremacy they convicted the body to squalidity. *"Physical activities and games would of course will be affected by the developments that led towards the industrial society"*. Kurt (1997)

In 1863, the imposing of gymnastics courses at the Turkish Military Academy, Naval School and Kuleli High School is the first step in our physical education courses. Then, with the Statute On General Education which was issued in 1869, this execution will be expanded to include the Ottoman junior high schools, so that sport will become a part of the physical education and formal education system to first, secularism and second independence, just as it is in the European Age of Enlightenment. Between 1863 and 1903, physical education courses started to be taught in schools despite lots of difficulties. (Fişek, 1985)

Along with westernization, physical education courses started at Robert College and Galatasaray High School. Physical education courses were taught by French teacher "Curel" and westerner sports were being taught in these courses. Selim Sırrı Tarcan who was sent to Sweden in 1909 and took sport education in there, then became a first physical education teacher, have physical education course put in curriculum of all schools. Fişek (1985) Tarcan, "Gymnastics Teachers Course" was opened in 1927-1928 academic year for girls and boys with a special year-long theoretical and practical training. In 1932, Gazi Secondary Training College Physical Education Department was opened. (Mirzeoğlu, 2011)

91 years after the establishment of the Republic, it is becoming difficult to understand and explain the removal of lessons while secondary education institutions need to make efforts to reach a healthier structure with physical education and sporting practices in the fields, facilities, equipment and teachers. The state and state governors who have removed physical education courses on the schools want to host large sports organizations like the Olympics. In line with this claim, only in İstanbul, 100 gyms from 100 benefactors' project were succeeded in 2013. While General Directorate of Youth and Sports started to increase sports facilities in cities and The Ministry of Health tried to use sport in getting healthy with the programs conducted for 3 years with schools and physical education teachers with campaigns against to obesity, science became the leader of these studies.

2. General Information

Along with globalization, democracy, human rights and freedom are all important attributes. However, as the "social" quality of the state is decreasing, sports investments are also declining. The concept of "rights" is being discussed in today's sport, which has a lot of commercial factors. Education, health, nutrition, sports are indispensable rights. The indispensable rights for every human being, regardless of who, in which situation, and how, are civil liberties and the sport is a civil liberty. Sports are a civil liberty because it is a essential requirement. While everyone is able to use the right to sports and to provide development opportunities to those who are capable reals the relationship between sport and democracy and sports-social development relations while revealing the state-sport relationship. (Erdemli, 2002) The concept of right is not evenly distributed to all the countries and peoples of the world. While the sport industry creates job opportunities in developed countries, it does not (Cambridge Econometrics, 2003) do underdeveloped countries such handsome.

"The sporting level of a society can also be measured by watching sports events of people in society, and this criterion is not at a level to be underestimated because sport; develop and empower the level of human life. Everyone in a society to do the right and constant sports allows to increase the quality of life of the community." (Erdemli, 2002) The basis of this approach was stated in constitution. This determination is carefully applied to schools. Physical education courses are indispensable element in the life of this basic philosophy. *"Sports training awaken and activate the person who does Sports inside the individual. Those who have*

sports skill and sports geniuses who will be discovered and revealed stay in sleep without sports education." (Erdemli, 2008)

The 59th article of the Constitution states that "*the State takes measures to improve the physical and mental health of Turkish citizens of all ages, encouraging the spread of sports to masses*". Apart from the Constitution, in the 2nd paragraph of 2nd article of the Basic Law of National Education No. 1739, the main aim of National Education is to raise people who have healthy and properly developed personality and character in terms of body, mental, moral, spirit and emotion and have independent and scientific power of thinking, respectful to human rights, value for personality and enterprise, responsible for community, positive, creative and productive. It is seen that removing the physical education course in the vocational high school is contrary to the Constitution and the Basic Law of National Education.

At the beginning of the 2009-2010 academic year, a similar practice took place in all high schools and physical education classes were elected. It was abandoned after a year on from the students, the parents and teachers, the physical education and sports teacher departments of our universities and the reactions from many civil society organizations. For all high school types except vocational high school grade 11, 2 hours of compulsory physical education classes were put in each class. At the end of the last three years, from 2012-2013, all the classes in the high school came to the point where they could take 2 hours of Physical Education course, with this decision, the education system was subverted and the physical education lesson in vocational education was removed again. Prior to this, with 4+4+4 system, our children were already deprived of physical education lessons and sports. Physical education courses from primary school to last grade of high school are the most important field that taught by doing, experiencing and should not to be changed. For vocational high school students, the physical education course has a much more special place. It is a right to want these students who work and produce every day of the week to have a discharge of 2 hours a week with physical education lessons, to play sports, to gain sports culture, to protect their health and to express themselves through sports. The removal of sports courses from professional high schools will not increase students' attitudes towards healthy living and healthy thinking and acquisition sports culture.

There are 20 million obese when research is viewed in Turkey. While the Ministry of Health has devoted resources under the name of "fight against obesity" and spent thousands of money on advertising films, drug addiction has reached even to primary schools, and violence in sport has become increasingly widespread in every field. Hospitals are filled with people suffering from joint discomforts, herniated disc, spinal cord injuries and sedentary lifestyle at a young age. It is a vital argument that our country and our young people will be struggling with these problems by depriving them of physical education and sports education and training to protect their health in a country where sports culture is not put in place and international sporting success is bottomed out.

In order to get the Olympics, the Ministry of Youth and Sports spend millions of liras to invest in campaigns and investments, while removing physical education

courses in the vocational high schools with the highest sporting achievements in school sports, and hosting Olympians by burying the potential athletes from the ground up? The number of active athletes in the population of 76 million is 549 972 women and 1 584 291 men. The total number of licensed athletes is 1 308 393 for women and 4127 for men in total 4 721 371. (gsgm.gov.tr). We can not hide the fact that we are a country that does not make sports for young people while praising with young population in Europe.

For a healthy generation, when will it be understood that bodily development is as important as spiritual development? In France, students have 1200 hours of physical education and sports lessons. This number is 960 in the UK and 720 hours in other European countries. It was 224 hours in Turkey.

The Government's sport policy does not provide the widest range of sporting events to promote health. The education policy of the government, when "the importance of education in terms of the future of community is considering" almost every field of religion has been added step by step by the MNE, from the formulation of the curriculum to the practical exercises. Aydoğanoğlu (2012) The government highlights sporting heroes, record sports and medal hunting. Medals and prizes are laid out in a non-moral way for athletes. The Government and the State are hosting many sports organizations with University Sports Games, World Basketball Championships, Black Sea Games, University Winter Games and finally Mediterranean Games. It is also a matter of commercial concern to host the Olympic Games as the primary sporting game. For that reason, it is possible to requested the reason of that the school sport which is a fundamental of the sport is considered as "work of devil" and prohibited in the country, but also there is a willing on hosting the sport organizations.

3. Discussion

With the resolution of Turkish Education Board of 23 January 2014 and numbered 2, the hours of Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry and Biology courses of vocational and technical secondary education institutions were increased. With the decision of The General Directorate of Vocational and Technical Education, the foreign language, physical education / music / visual arts courses which are being taught in all the secondary education institutions and which are among the common courses for some classes were removed. According to this; 2 hours physical education courses in 10 grade in Vocational high schools and Anatolian vocational high schools, 2 hours physical education courses in in 10 grade in Technical high schools and Anatolian technical high schools, 1 hour physical education / visual arts / music courses in 10 grade in Urgent Health Care Services, Anesthesia And Reanimation, Environmental Health, Dental Prosthesis, Medical Secretary, Medical Laboratory And Radiology Departments of Anatolian medical vocational high school, 3 hours foreign language course and 1 hour physical education / visual arts / music course in Orthopaedic Prosthesis and Orthosis department in Anatolian medical vocational high schools and 3 hours foreign language course and 1 hour physical education/visual arts/music course in 10 grades in Nursing

department of Anatolian Health Vocational Schools were removed. In addition, elective courses taught in these classes have been removed. In addition to elective courses not taught in all secondary schools and not included in common courses, it is necessary for us, teaching sport education, to evaluate the removing of courses of foreign language, physical education / music / visual arts which are being taught in all secondary education institutions and which are among the common courses.

The 2nd article of the National Education Basic Law numbered 1739 is the main purposes of national education were stated. One of them is *“Raising people who have healthy and properly developed personality and character in terms of body, mental, moral, spirit and emotion and have independent and scientific power of thinking, respectful to human rights, value for personality and enterprise, responsible for community, positive, creative and productive.”* the other one is, *“Developing their interests, ability and skills and bring them habits such as necessary knowledge, skills, behaviors and working together and prepare them for life and ensuring them to have a occupation which will make them happy and contribute to happiness of community.”* In accordance with Article 3 of the same Law, the Turkish education and training system will be regulated in such a way as to achieve these general objectives and will be determined in accordance with the specific aims, general objectives and basic principles of the various degrees and types of educational institutions.

In the 5th article titled 'Principles' of the Regulation for the Regulation of the Secondary Education Institutions of the Ministry of National Education, which entered into force after the publication of the Official Gazette No. 28758 on 7 September 2013; the provision that *“The functions of secondary education institutions are in line with universal principles, democracy and human rights in line with the basic principles of Turkish national education for general and special purposes and fulfill student-centered, active learning and democratic institutional culture”* took place. In the Article 7/1-a entitled 'The aims of secondary education institutions' of same regulation, *“To develop students in terms of physical, mental, moral, spiritual, social and cultural qualities, respect for democracy and human rights, preparing them for the future by equipping them with the knowledge and skills required by our day”* considered as the common aims of secondary school institutions. In the study conducted by the faculty member Recep Özkan in 2012; It has been reached that these courses are the lessons that students can express themselves, improve their creativity, improve their aesthetic development, gain self-confidence and to contribute most to the students in terms of their period, that the courses of painting, music and physical education are among the courses that support the physical, mental and emotional development of the students.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

As a result; in vocational education, the removing of physical education courses should be abandoned. As it is known, the two-hour physical education courses in the 10 grade have been abolished in order to make room for courses in physics, chemistry, biology and mathematics in vocational education. The fact that the courses such as philosophy,

sociology, painting, music and physical education are the first lessons to be drawn from within the educational program reveals the irregularity of the Ministry of Education's educational point of view. Those who form educational policies have reduced the contents of painting, music and physical education lessons to raise individuals in line with the official ideology. However, these courses are important courses that should be built upon the awareness and free development of students' creativity and abilities. For this reason, MNE, who has announced that students will take their talents as a basis for transition to secondary education and higher education at every opportunity do not refrain to prevent art and sport courses that need to be organized in order to develop their talents and creativity, thus declaring how unimportant these courses are.

Removing of physical education, music, painting / visual arts courses contrary to the basic aims and principles of national education specified in the National Education Basic Law and the Ministry of National Education Regulation on Secondary Education Institutions and it will also prevent students from developing in terms of physical, mental, moral, spiritual, social and cultural qualities. Another problem posed by the regulation is related to the physical education teachers. There is no doubt that this arrangement will lead to a higher number of teachers and fewer physical education teacher assignments. With the restructured 4 + 4 + 4 system in 2013, 4200 classroom teachers made physical education teachers in one day. At the 2013 and 2014 appointments, the numbers of physical education teachers were greatly reduced. The study of about 20,000 physical education teachers in 70,000 schools proves that the state is consider the sports and sports educator wrongly.

70 thousand schools should have 70 thousand physical education teachers. It should be seen that MNE has signed the policies that ignore not only the students but also the teachers. As a sports scientist, we emphasize that once again in every environment that the MEB should abandon its attitude of "I made it very well" on a topic such as education that deals with the vast majority of the society. The physical education course which is related to all learning areas within the multiple intelligence theory is a discipline that must be at least 2 hours a week compulsory and 2 hours a total of 4 hours within the scope of compulsory joint courses from the pre-school education attached to the Ministry of National Education until the end of 12th grade. The Turkish Education Board should step back from its decision if it believes it is necessary to train with training (exercise, play, physical activity) or resign if not. No school type can exempt and debar from this course. The mandatory 2 hours physical education course that was removed in vocational high school should be re-introduced to all classes and the physical education course should be taught by branch teachers. The name of the Physical Education course should be changed to Game and Sports education.

As entering a new educational period, a minister of education says very nice words. But it is his duty to overcome contradictions in execution. During the dark ages of the Middle Ages, the "*physical exercise is the work of the devil*" were the bigoted religious ecclesiastics of the Catholic Church. What about us?

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